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Highly selective base-catalyzed ring closing Ugi-adducts from the reaction of 2-formylindole, 2-bromoacetic acid, amines and isocyanides

[Morteza Shiri](#), Zahra Bozorgpour-Savadjani

*Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Alzahra University, 1993893973 Vanak, Tehran, Iran.
e-mail: mshiri@alzahra.ac.ir*

Abstract

The intermediate products of the Ugi reaction between indole-2-carboxaldehyde, 2-bromoacetic acid, amines and isocyanides were treated with Cs₂CO₃ in DMF to form a series of novel cyclized 1,2-dihydropyrazino[1,2a]indol-3(4H)-ones (indole –NH cyclization) as major and piperazin-2-ones (amide –NH cyclization) as minor products.

Keywords: Multicomponent condensation reactions, Indole, Base-catalyzed cyclization, Pyrazino[1,2a]indolone.